

CRACK OPENING DISPLACEMENT AS A BASIC PARAMETER FOR STIFFNESS REDUCTION MODELING IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Stiffness reduction in $[S,90_n]_s$ laminates due to transverse cracking in 90-layers is modeled. Closed form expressions for axial modulus and Poisson's ratio reduction as the crack density increases are obtained. These expressions are convenient for use and they contain, apart from crack density, geometrical parameters and elastic constants of layers, only the average opening displacement of the transverse crack (COD) that is normalized with respect to far field strain and 90-layer thickness. The average COD is calculated using FEM in plane stress formulation. The constraint effect of adjacent layers, influence of crack spacing and the effect of out-of-plane elastic constants on COD are studied. Simple power law relating average COD to the elastic and geometrical parameters is derived based on results of parametric analysis. This relationship is successfully used to predict the axial modulus and Poisson's ratio reduction in $(\pm\theta,90_4)_s$ laminates.

KEYWORDS: symmetric laminates, transverse cracks, stiffness reduction, finite elements, crack opening displacement, analytical model.

INTRODUCTION

Laminated composites containing unidirectional layers of different fiber orientation show inelastic macro-response during thermo-mechanical loading. The observed stiffness change is caused by ply level micro-damage in form of intra-laminar cracks, local delaminations etc. Micromechanical modeling of the stiffness reduction due to transverse cracks has a long history starting from simple shear lag models [1] and going further to more sophisticated variational models [2,3]. Analytical models have been used more than numerical and the application has been limited with cross-ply laminates. Numerical solutions has been basically concerned with particular stress problem for a given laminate configuration without trying to obtain more general conclusions that would benefit the development of engineering methods.

However, it would be of great importance to derive closed form expressions for stiffness reduction of general symmetric laminates that contain only geometry, elastic properties and crack density. Exact solution does not exist for a general case. However, the effect of different factors, like the constraint of adjacent layers, could be evaluated approximately based on parametric analysis performed using FEM. Crucial for this approach is the

validation of the obtained results comparing with experimental data for as many particular cases as possible.

Recently it has been shown [4] using continuum damage modeling and experimental observations, that the basic parameter for stiffness reduction prediction in multidirectional laminates is the opening displacement of transverse cracks. In [5] a closed form expressions were derived for stiffness reduction in general symmetric laminates due to cracks in 90-layer. The only function from stress analysis entering these relationships is normalized average crack opening displacement. It was shown in [5] that analytical micromechanical models [1,2,3] may be generalized to treat the case of $[S,90_n]_s$ laminate and to obtain the necessary average COD.

In the presented paper we perform numerical FE parametric analysis of the effect of several elastic and geometrical parameters of layer and sublaminates (S) on COD. In a systematic way we analyze and conclude which elastic and geometrical parameters are of importance and which are not. These conclusions allow to simplify analysis of laminates with more complicated geometry. It appears that a simple power law can describe the effect of “important parameters”. Finally the stiffness reduction in complex laminates is analyzed using the previously obtained closed form expressions with average crack COD from derived semi-empirical power law. This approach is applied with excellent results to $[\pm\theta, 90_4]_s$ laminates.

MODELING STIFFNESS REDUCTION

GENERAL EXPRESSIONS FOR STIFFNESS REDUCTION.

We consider symmetric and balanced $[S, 90_n]_s$ laminate, consisting of two balanced sub-laminates as outer layers and cracked 90⁰-layer in the middle. The spacing between cracks is assumed to be equidistant, as shown in Fig. 1. The sub-laminates are macroscopically orthotropic in (x,y,z) -system but 90-layer is transversally isotropic. In following y -direction is perpendicular to (x,z) -plane, symbol $(\bar{\cdot})$ – denotes volume average over the volume where function is defined, indexes 90 and s correspond to the 90-layer and sub-laminate, respectively.

Fig. 1: Schematic showing of the laminate with cracks in 90-layer.

Constitutive equations are:

a) orthotropic sub-laminate S

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x^s \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_y^s \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_z^s \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{xx}^s & S_{xy}^s & S_{xz}^s \\ S_{xy}^s & S_{yy}^s & S_{yz}^s \\ S_{xz}^s & S_{yz}^s & S_{zz}^s \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x^s \\ \sigma_y^s \\ \sigma_z^s \end{Bmatrix} \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{xy}^s = S_{66}^s \sigma_{xy}^s, \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{xz}^s = S_{55}^s \sigma_{xz}^s, \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{yz}^s = S_{44}^s \sigma_{yz}^s \quad (1)$$

b) transversely isotropic 90⁰-layer

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x^{90} \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_y^{90} \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_z^{90} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{22} & S_{12} & S_{23} \\ S_{12} & S_{11} & S_{12} \\ S_{23} & S_{12} & S_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x^{90} \\ \sigma_y^{90} \\ \sigma_z^{90} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{xy}^{90} = S_{66} \sigma_{xy}^{90}, \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{xz}^{90} = S_{44} \sigma_{xz}^{90}, \quad \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{yz}^{90} = S_{66} \sigma_{yz}^{90} \quad (2)$$

Here S_{ij}^s is the compliance matrix of the sub-laminate and S_{ij} is the compliance matrix of unidirectional composite.

Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the laminate with cracks are defined as follows:

$$E_x = \frac{\sigma}{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x} \quad \nu_{xy} = -\frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_y^{-s}}{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x} \quad (3)$$

Equation
$$\frac{E_x}{E_{x0}} = \frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{x0}}{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x} \quad (4)$$

shows that in order to obtain expression for stiffness reduction we need to compare (at the same applied composite stress σ) average strains of the laminate without and with cracks. In following we will use nondimensional coordinates:

$$\bar{z} = \frac{z}{d} \quad \bar{x} = \frac{x}{d} \quad \bar{l}_0 = \frac{l_0}{d} \quad \bar{b} = \frac{b}{d} \quad \bar{h} = \frac{h}{d} \quad h = b + d \quad (5)$$

In analysis we use [5] integral force equilibrium in z and y -directions (force is zero), integral force equilibrium in x -direction and generalized plane strain conditions in y -direction.

Using these assumptions average strains in (3) ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x^{-90}$, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x^{-s}$ and also $\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_y$) may be expressed through average x -axis stresses in 90-layer and in sublaminate [5].

Next we consider the average stresses $\bar{\sigma}_x^{-90}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_x^{-s}$ and analyze their relationship to the applied load σ , see Fig.1. Without losing generality the axial stress distribution, may be written in the following form:

$$\sigma_x^{90} = \sigma_{x0}^{90} - \sigma_{x0}^{90} f_1(\bar{x}, \bar{z}) \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_x^s = \sigma_{x0}^s + \sigma_{x0}^{90} f_2(\bar{x}, \bar{z}), \quad (7)$$

where σ_{x0}^{90} is the stress in 90-layer and σ_{x0}^s is the stress in the sub-laminate before cracking (obtained using laminate theory routine), $-\sigma_{x0}^{90} f_1(\bar{x}, \bar{z})$ and $\sigma_{x0}^{90} f_2(\bar{x}, \bar{z})$ are stress perturbations caused by the presence of the cracks. Averaging (6) and (7) and using the integral force equilibrium in x -direction we obtain

$$\bar{\sigma}_x^{-90} = \sigma_{x0}^{90} - \sigma_{x0}^{90} \frac{1}{2\bar{l}_0} R(\bar{l}_0) \quad (8)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_x^{-s} = \sigma_{x0}^s + \sigma_{x0}^{90} \frac{1}{2\bar{l}_0 \bar{b}} R(\bar{l}_0) \quad (9)$$

Function
$$R(\bar{l}_0) = \int_{-\bar{l}_0}^{+\bar{l}_0} \int_{-1}^1 f_1(\bar{x}, \bar{z}) d\bar{z} d\bar{x} \quad (10)$$

is called in following the stress perturbation function. It is a function of the crack spacing (crack density).

Average x-axis stresses are now expressed through the stress perturbation function (10). Substituting (8) and (9) into previously obtained expressions for average strains we obtain

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_x^{-s} = \varepsilon_{x0} + \sigma_{x0}^{90} \frac{d}{2\bar{l}_0 b} R(\bar{l}_0) \left(S_{xx}^s - \frac{S_{xy}^s (S_{xy}^s d + S_{12} b)}{S_{yy}^s d + S_{11} b} \right) \quad (11)$$

$$\varepsilon_y = \varepsilon_{y0} + \sigma_{x0}^{90} \frac{d}{2\bar{l}_0} R(\bar{l}_0) \frac{S_{xy}^s S_{11} - S_{12} S_{yy}^s}{S_{yy}^s d + S_{11} b} \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_x^{-90} = \varepsilon_{x0} + \sigma_{x0}^{90} \frac{1}{2\bar{l}_0} R(\bar{l}_0) \left(S_{22} - \frac{S_{12} (S_{12} b + S_{xy} d)}{S_{yy}^s d + S_{11} b} \right) \quad (13)$$

Equations (11)-(13) apart from crack spacing \bar{l}_0 and stress perturbation function $R(\bar{l}_0)$ contain only the far field solution, constituent properties and geometry. The far field stress component σ_{x0}^{90} can be expressed through ε_{x0} using Classical Laminate Theory:

$$\sigma_{x0}^{90} = Q_{22}^{CLT} \varepsilon_{x0} + Q_{12}^{CLT} \varepsilon_{y0} = \varepsilon_{x0} Q_{22}^{CLT} (1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{xy}^0) \quad (14)$$

Here ν_{xy}^0 is the Poisson's ratio of the undamaged laminate, Q_{ij}^{CLT} - stiffness matrix elements of layer in material symmetry axes according to laminate theory and ν_{12} - Poisson's ratio of the layer.

Using (14) in (11)-(13) and substituting the result in (3) and (4) we see that elastic properties of laminate with a given crack density in 90-layer can be now calculated:

$$\frac{E_x}{E_{x0}} = \frac{1}{1 + a\rho R(\bar{l}_0)} \quad \nu_{xy}^0 = \frac{1 - c\rho R(\bar{l}_0)}{1 + a\rho R(\bar{l}_0)} \quad (15)$$

Here $\rho = \frac{1}{2l_0}$ is a given crack density and a, c are known functions of elastic properties and geometry of the sub-laminate and 90⁰-layer:

$$a = \frac{E_2 d}{E_x^s b} \quad c = \frac{E_2 d}{\nu_{xy}^0} \left(\frac{S_{xy}^s S_{11} - S_{12} S_{yy}^s}{S_{yy}^s d + S_{11} b} \right) \quad (16)$$

From (16) follows that the perturbation function $R(\bar{l}_0)$ is the only still unknown function. The rate of the stiffness reduction depends on the form of this function. It is not only a function of crack spacing but also depends on elastic properties and geometry as far they can effect the stress perturbation. In order to establish the role and significance of different parameters in the remaining part of this paper we will analyze this function using FE method.

AVERAGE COD RELATION TO STRESS PERTURBATION FUNCTION

Contrary to the most commonly used approximate methods [1,2,3] standard FEM procedure is based on displacement formulation. Therefore the displacement distribution (crack opening displacements in our case) is generally obtained more accurate than stress distributions. We will take advantage from this feature by establishing unique relationship

between the stress perturbation function in question and the average opening displacement of the crack (COD) normalized in proper way. The average normalized COD is defined in following way:

$$\bar{u}_a = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_{x0} d} \int_0^1 u(\bar{z}) d\bar{z}. \quad (17)$$

Here ε_{x0} is the far field strain, which corresponds to the force applied to the laminate in FE calculation. It may be shown [5] that the average COD can be expressed in the following way:

$$\bar{u}_a = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_{x0} d} l_0 \left(\bar{\varepsilon}_x^s - \bar{\varepsilon}_x^{90^\circ} \right) \quad (18)$$

Substituting (11)-(13) into (18) we obtain

$$R(\bar{J}_0) = k \bar{u}_a, \quad (19)$$

Here

$$\frac{1}{k} = E_2 \frac{d}{2b} \left[S_{xx}^s + \frac{b}{d} S_{22} - \frac{(S_{xy}^s d + S_{12} b)^2}{d(S_{yy}^s d + S_{11} b)} \right] \quad (20)$$

The obtained proportionality between the stress perturbation function, $R(\bar{J}_0)$ and the average normalized COD may be used to present stiffness reduction expressions (15), in a new form using \bar{u}_a instead of the stress perturbation function

$$\frac{E_x}{E_{x0}} = \frac{1}{1 + ak\rho \bar{u}_a} \quad \frac{v_{xy}}{v_{xy}^0} = \frac{1 - ck\rho \bar{u}_a}{1 + ak\rho \bar{u}_a} \quad (21)$$

The plane stress state simulation in cracked laminate was performed using commercial finite element code NISA. Based on symmetry considerations only a quarter of the representative element was used for 2D finite element analysis. We have symmetry conditions on sides $x = -l_0, z \in [d, h]$ and $x \in [-l_0, 0], z = 0$. Traction free- conditions are on $z = h$ and on the crack surface $x = -l_0, z \in [0, d]$, Finally applied constant displacement in x -direction, on $x = 0, z \in [0, h]$. The 2D four- node quadratic (correspondingly 6 and 8 node) plane elements were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section consists of two parts. In the first part we will discuss the average normalized COD and its dependence on geometrical and elastic parameters of constituents. In the second part we will use the obtained information about COD's in order to predict the stiffness reduction in $[S, 90_n]_s$ laminates.

Normalized COD

Performed FE calculations correspond to 0.4% average strain applied to the element between two cracks. Thermal effects are not included in analysis. Note, that in case of varying element length l_0 , the same applied average strain corresponds to different levels of applied load (laminate stress). The situation that FEM solutions correspond to different applied loads (and, hence, to different far field stress levels in 90-layer) complicate the analysis of the crack interaction. To overcome this problem we will always normalize the obtained COD's with respect to the far field strain value corresponding to the actual load applied to the element with length l_0 , see (17).

Calculations are performed for brittle and toughened glass fiber/epoxy (called Std GF/EP and GF/EP) and carbon fiber/epoxy C30/922 materials with properties given in Table 1.

Table 1: Elastic properties of glass fiber/epoxy and carbon fiber/epoxy C30/922 composites.

Property	Std GF/EP	GF/EP	Carbon C30/922
E_1 (GPa)	45.5	44.73	137.9
E_2 (GPa)	12.7	12.76	8.6
ν_{12}	0.28	0.297	0.3
ν_{23}^*	0.42	0.42	0.49
G_{12} (GPa)	3.45	5.80	7.1
G_{23} (GPa)*	4.5	4.49	6.21

* assumed value

The average normalized COD's \bar{u}_a (17) are shown in Table 2 for Std GF/EP laminates and for C30/922 laminates. We see that in Std GF/EP \bar{u}_a is approximately 20% higher than in carbon fiber/epoxy C30/922 laminates. For typical crack densities the crack spacing \bar{l}_0 has a very small effect on \bar{u}_a for both materials.

Table 2: Average normalized COD \bar{u}_a of Std GF/EP and CF/EP C30/922 laminates.

Std GF/EP			C30/922			
lo/d	FEM [0,90 ₂]s	FEM [0 ₂ ,90 ₂]s	lo/d	FEM [0,90 ₂]s	FEM [0 ₂ ,90 ₂]s	FEM [0 ₄ ,90 ₂]s
8	1.399	1.248	8	1.081	1.025	1.003
4	1.391	1.250	4	1.082	1.034	1.018
3	1.394	1.261	3	1.088	1.049	1.030
2	1.396	1.238	2	1.083	1.029	1.004
1.5	1.330	1.143	1.5	1.011	0.955	0.933

Reduction is noticeable only for $\bar{l}_0=1.5$ which corresponds to rather high crack density. This observation allows reducing significantly the number of FEM calculations needed for predictions. Increasing the thickness ratio b/d the COD's are reduced. This effect is smaller for C30/922 ($\approx 8\%$) than for Std GF/EP laminates ($\approx 13\%$). It should be noticed that according to (21) 10% difference of \bar{u}_a lead to approximately the same difference of calculated slope of stiffness change.

Based on results presented above we conclude: a) \bar{u}_a in rather wide crack spacing region is not sensitive to \bar{l}_0 and FE calculation is necessary for only one crack density $\bar{l}_0 = 4$; b) increasing 0-layer stiffness and larger 0- to 90-layer thickness ratio reduce the \bar{u}_a .

In order to understand the significance of the axial stiffness ratio and layer thickness ratio on COD we performed parametric analysis using elastic properties listed in Table 3 and considering only one crack spacing $\bar{l}_0 = 4$. The calculated \bar{u}_a as a function of E_x^s/E_x^{90} is shown in Fig.2a. Three different sublaminates thicknesses are considered. Indexes at S in the laminate code denote the sublaminates thickness, for example, [S₂,90₄]s means that the

sublaminates thickness is 2 as compared with the 90-layer half-thickness 4 ($b=2, d=4$ in Fig.1).

Table 3: Elastic properties of constituents used in parametric analysis.

Constituent	E_x (Gpa)	E_z (Gpa)	ν_{xz}	G_{xz} (Gpa)
90-layer	10	10	0.35	3.7
Sublaminates	$E_x^s = 10, 20, 50, 70, 110, 150, 250$ or 400	10	0.3	3.5

Fig.2: Average COD dependence on layer stiffness ratio. a) FE calculated; b) FE+ eq.(22).

Obtained curves may be fitted by power functions in form

$$\bar{u}_a = A + B \left(\frac{E_x^s}{E_x^{90}} \right)^{-\alpha} \quad (22)$$

Applying linear fit to calculated data in log-log axes we obtain values $A=0.955$ and $\alpha = 0.9$ independent on thickness ratio,

$$B = 0.9102 + 0.3413 \frac{d-b}{b} \quad (23)$$

Fig.2b show FEM COD's and ones calculated using $A=0.955, \alpha = 0.9, (22)$ and (23) . Agreement is good.

Parametric analysis was performed in order to determine the effect of $G_{xz}^s, \nu_{xz}^s, \nu_{xz}^s$ on the average crack opening displacement. Results presented in Table 4 show that the effect is negligible. Hence, the usual uncertainty in out-of-plane properties has a very small effect on predictions.

Table 4: Effect of G_{xz}^s , ν_{TT}^s , ν_{xz}^s on average normalized COD \bar{u}_a in $[S_4,90_4]_s$ laminates.

E_x^s / E_x^{90}	$G_{xz}^s = 3.5$ GPA	$G_{xz}^s = 4.5$ GPA	E_x^s / E_x^{90}	$\nu_{TT}^s = 0.35$	$\nu_{TT}^s = 0.49$	E_x^s / E_x^{90}	$\nu_{xz}^s = 0.3$	$\nu_{xz}^s = 0.33$
2.0	1.4507	1.4507	2.0	1.4507	1.4424	20	1.4507	1.4514
5.0	1.1759	1.1759	5.0	1.1759	1.1716	50	1.1759	1.1759
7.0	1.1185	1.1185	7.0	1.1185	1.1158	70	1.1185	1.1185
11.0	1.0641	1.0640	11.0	1.0641	1.0634	110	1.0641	1.0639
15.0	1.0376	1.0375	15.0	1.0376	1.0382	150	1.0376	1.0374
25.0	1.0072	1.0072	25.0	1.0072	1.0098	250	1.0072	1.0072

Stiffness reduction prediction.

We consider $[\pm\theta, 90_4]_s$ laminates with material properties given in Table 1 (GF/EP). Sublaminate is $(\pm\theta)$ with $\theta=0$ and 30 . Calculated engineering constants and normalized average COD's are in Table 7. \bar{u}_a is calculated using (22), (23). Calculated \bar{u}_a and other elastic constants in Table 5 are used to predict the reduction of longitudinal stiffness and Poisson's ratio of the laminate due to increasing crack density in 90-layer, see equation (21).

Table 5 Sublaminate properties and average crack opening displacement

Angle θ	E_x^s (GPa)	E_z^s (Gpa)	ν_{xz}^s	G_{xz}	E_{XS}/E_T	\bar{u}_a ($\pm\theta,90_4$)s
0	44.73	12.76	0.297	5.8	3.5	1.355
30	27.23	13.45	0.182	5.47	2	1.630

Predictions and experimental data for longitudinal modulus and Poisson's ratio reduction as crack density increases are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. Agreement between experimental data and model predictions is very good.

Fig. 3: Stiffness reduction in GF/EP $(0_2,90_4)_s$ cross-ply laminate.

- a) Longitudinal modulus;
- b) Poisson's ratio

Fig. 4 Stiffness reduction in GF/EP (30,-30,90₄)_s laminate.
a) Longitudinal modulus;
b) Poisson's ratio.

CONCLUSIONS

Closed form expressions for stiffness reduction in $[S,90_n]_s$ laminates due to transverse cracking in 90-layers are derived. They contain, apart from crack density, geometrical parameters and elastic constants of layers, only the average opening displacement of the transverse crack (COD) that is normalized with respect to far field strain and 90-layer thickness.

The average COD is calculated using FEM in plane stress formulation. The constraint effect of adjacent layers, influence of crack spacing and the effect of out-of-plane elastic constants on COD are studied in a systematic manner. It is found that out-of-plane elastic constants have a very little effect on COD. Simple power law relating average COD to the elastic and geometrical parameters is derived based on results of parametric analysis.

These conclusions allow to simplify analysis of laminates with more complex geometry. The obtained power law was successfully used to predict the axial modulus and Poisson's ratio reduction in $(\pm\theta,90_4)_s$ laminates.

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